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*COMPETENCIES AND INNOVATION: APPLICATION OF THE FIVE-V TOOL
IN A COLLABORATIVE NANO-ENTERPRISE¹*

**COMPETÊNCIAS E INOVAÇÃO: APLICAÇÃO DA FERRAMENTA FIVE-V
EM UM NANOEMPREENHIMENTO DE LOJA COLABORATIVA**

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to present the application of the Five-V tool, originally designed for medium and large companies, to nano-enterprises, focusing on reshaping their business models to foster innovation. As a case study, a nano-enterprise exhibitor in a collaborative store in Brasília-DF was analyzed, with an emphasis on value reconfiguration. The Five-V tool, proposed by Taran et al., was used to answer the following question: What entrepreneurial competencies are necessary to promote innovation in the business model of AbA? As results, the study presents an illustration of the proposed new business model for the nano-enterprise, as well as a framework of the essential competencies for implementing this innovation. The application of the tool provided an expanded view of the AbA brand's values and identified the necessary behaviors for transforming the business model. This work demonstrates the feasibility and benefits of adapting strategic tools, traditionally used by larger companies, to the context of nano-enterprises, contributing to the advancement of the debate on innovation and management in small businesses.

Keywords: five-v, innovation, entrepreneurial skills, nanoentrepreneurship.

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RESUMO

Este trabalho tem como objetivo apresentar a aplicação da ferramenta Five-V, originalmente desenvolvida para médias e grandes empresas, em nanoempreendimentos, com foco na remodelagem de seus modelos de negócio em prol da inovação. Como estudo de caso, foi analisado um nanoempreendimento expositor em uma loja colaborativa de Brasília-DF, com ênfase na reconfiguração de valor. A ferramenta Five-V, proposta por Taran et al., foi utilizada para responder à seguinte questão: Quais as competências empreendedoras necessárias para promover a inovação no modelo de negócios da AbA? Como resultados, o estudo apresenta uma ilustração do novo modelo de negócios proposto para o nanoempreendimento, bem como um quadro das competências essenciais para a implementação dessa inovação. A aplicação da ferramenta permitiu uma visão ampliada dos valores da marca AbA e identificou os comportamentos necessários para a transformação do modelo de negócios. Este trabalho demonstra a viabilidade e os benefícios da adaptação de ferramentas estratégicas, tradicionalmente utilizadas por empresas de maior porte, para o contexto dos nanoempreendimentos, contribuindo para o avanço do debate sobre inovação e gestão em pequenos negócios.

Palavras-chave: five-v, inovação, competências empreendedoras, nanoempreendedorismo.

INTRODUCTION

The recent publication of Complementary Law No. 214, dated January 16, 2025, sanctioned by President Luiz Inácio Lula da Silva, formalized the term “nano-entrepreneur” in an effort to reduce informality and promote legality in the small business market. Facing a scenario with approximately 40 million informal workers in the country, according to data from the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE), these entrepreneurs face significant challenges, such as difficulties in accessing credit, social benefits, labor rights, and consequently, in expanding their businesses.

This work gains relevance by addressing nano-entrepreneurs through a case study to apply tools and methodologies of business models that can assist in maintaining and growing their enterprises. Implementing a new business model requires specific entrepreneurial behaviors, raising the following question: What

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are the entrepreneurial competencies necessary to promote innovation in the business model of AbA Arte Design?

The objective of this study is to answer this question through the application of the Five-V tool, proposed by Taran et al., in a nano-enterprise exhibiting in a collaborative store in Brasília-DF. AbA Arte Design, a brand born with the purpose of printing personalized products with original images, was chosen as the case study. Initially, the business faced difficulties, with low product sales volume threatening its viability. However, in 2016, the creation of a series of paintings with different interpretations of Brasília monuments won over the public in 2018, becoming the brand's main differentiator and niche, representing 95% of the products currently sold.

Like most nano-enterprises, AbA Arte Design faces ongoing challenges, such as financial management, commercial seasonality, and the constant need for innovation. To help overcome these obstacles, the Five-V tool was applied, a strategic methodology based on five categories of analysis: value proposition, value segment, value configuration, value network, and value capture. The purpose is to innovate the product offering and structure business management.

Developed by Taran et al., the Five-V is a business modeling and innovation tool traditionally applied to medium and large companies. This work, however, explores its adaptation to a nano-enterprise, demonstrating its viability and potential to promote innovation in small businesses. Additionally, the entrepreneurial competencies necessary for successful implementation of the new business model are discussed, based on contributions from authors such as Queiroz (2008) and Fillion (1993).

The structure of this article includes the presentation of fundamental concepts, such as nano-entrepreneurship, collaborative stores, entrepreneurial competencies, and the Five-V tool, followed by the analysis of the results

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obtained with the application of the tool and the competencies identified as essential for innovation in AbA Arte Design's business model.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

Collaborative stores as spaces for nano-entrepreneurs

Collaborative stores are excellent opportunities for testing and experimentation for beginner entrepreneurs, especially creatives, offering opportunities for local entrepreneurs through shared costs and services. They serve as a barometer for new ventures. These stores provide opportunities for development, growth, and expansion for emerging brands, stimulating creativity and innovation so customers appreciate the exhibiting brands.

These stores feature shared physical spaces among nano and micro-entrepreneurs who pay rent for this space (commonly called "caixinha") and a percentage of sales to cover various expenses such as administrative fees and attendants. They generally house more than 40 "brands" of small businesses.

These spaces, called "caixinhas," come in different forms: shelves, niches, racks, display windows, counters, etc., hosting a wide variety of products such as crafts, souvenirs, stationery, accessories, jewelry, clothing, keepsakes, plants, sweets, beverages, and more.

This is a growing and popular business model in recent years in Brazil. The Endossa store, founded in São Paulo in 2008, is considered the first collaborative store in Brazil and a pioneer in this model. Based on renting physical spaces for product and service displays from very small enterprises, ranging from nano-entrepreneurs to MEIs (Individual Micro-Entrepreneurs) and even micro-entrepreneurs, the concept originated in Europe (SEBRAE).

Exhibiting entrepreneurs who participate in these collaborative stores are called "brands." The collaborative store houses "brands," whether individuals or

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companies, allowing freelancers, designers, artists, artisans, writers, and creatives to rent spaces to promote their brands.

But what exactly is nano-entrepreneurship?

With approximately 40 million informal workers, according to IBGE, a large portion of this population in Brazil faces difficulties accessing credit, social benefits, and labor rights.

Recently published, Complementary Law number 214, of January 16, 2025, sanctioned by President Luiz Inácio Lula da Silva on the 16th of the same month, formalized the definition of the term in an attempt to bring legality to nano-entrepreneurs, reducing informality. The aforementioned law establishes the Tax on Goods and Services (IBS), the Social Contribution on Goods and Services (CBS), and the Selective Tax (IS); creates the IBS Management Committee and amends tax legislation. (BRAZIL, 2025)

In its Article 26, Item IV, it presents the term as follows:

IV - nano-entrepreneur, understood as a natural person who has earned gross revenue less than 50% (fifty percent) of the limit established for joining the MEI regime provided for in § 1 of art. 18-A, also observing the provisions of §§ 4 and 4-B of the aforementioned article of Complementary Law No. 123, of December 14, 2006, and has not joined this regime (BRAZIL, 2025).

Complementing this in your tenth paragraph:

§ 10. For the purposes of classification as a nano-entrepreneur, under the terms of item IV of the heading of this article, the gross revenue of the individual providing private individual passenger transport services or delivery of goods mediated by digital platforms will be considered to be 25% (twenty-five percent) of the gross monthly amount received (BRAZIL, 2025).

This model, aimed at freelancers and very small businesses, seeks to streamline processes, expand economic inclusion, value low-income activities, and bring social benefits to these entrepreneurs who are exempt from the new taxes created by the tax reform, such as the IBS and CBS, as well as greater

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visibility and competitiveness, increasing consumption and stimulating local development.

The annual revenue for nano-entrepreneurs must be up to R\$ 40,500.00, half the revenue of a Micro Individual Entrepreneur – MEI (currently R\$ 81,000.00). With simpler formalization and a lower tax burden, nano-entrepreneurs will operate as individuals, without the need to create a CNPJ, in addition to a differentiated tax regime for professionals on digital platforms, such as app drivers and delivery workers.

Among the main beneficiaries are: day laborers, street vendors, seamstresses, artisans, gardeners, cooks, family farmers, motorcycle taxi drivers and self-employed delivery drivers, including informal workers with annual revenue of up to R\$ 40,500.00, and professionals from digital platforms who do not qualify for MEI (Individual Microentrepreneur).

Nano-entrepreneurs will not pay the Value Added Tax (VAT) created by the tax reform, which replaces ICMS, ISS, PIS, Cofins and IPI, ensuring that these entrepreneurs are not burdened with taxes they cannot afford, encouraging them to formalize their businesses. However, the exemption does not mean that they will not pay any taxes from 2026 onwards, the year in which the tax reform comes into effect; other contributions, such as social security contributions and property taxes, may be charged.

Professions such as lawyers, architects, accountants, engineers, advertising professionals, among others, will not be eligible to be classified as nano-entrepreneurs.

Drivers and delivery workers for apps, due to the high operational costs of these activities, will only have 25% of their gross revenue considered as income for classification purposes, meaning they can have an annual revenue of up to R\$ 162,000.

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Nano-entrepreneurship is present in the Brazilian market, in our daily lives and routines, especially in scenarios of economic instability. It is within the circle of friends and family, whether for the purpose of fulfilling a dream, supplementing income, or even out of necessity. It is commonly a "one-person business," a business responsible for moving financial resources, contributing directly to the country's economy. Common in low-income families impacted by financial crises, it makes selling services and products one of the most viable and dignified ways to generate income.

They are commonly not included in entrepreneurship statistics because formalization is not part of the reality for most of these entrepreneurs, making their challenges perhaps greater, but certainly different from those faced by other entrepreneurs, such as: pricing, financial and organizational management, brand positioning, building social capital, time commitment, communication, among others.

The growth in nano-entrepreneurship was mainly marked by the pandemic in 2020, impacting all types of entrepreneurs, and continues to this day, also affecting nano-entrepreneurs, as the lack of formal job opportunities motivated many to start their own business.

Nomadic entrepreneurs can also be part of the nano-entrepreneur niche. They don't have a fixed location and take their products to customers (like peddlers did and do), whether to customers' homes or at fairs and events where their products, goods, and services can be displayed. Even with the advancement of the internet and the possibilities of online sales, a communicative, welcoming, and diverse profile, along with contact with the public, are advantages in this niche. This ranges from clothing, handicrafts, accessories, and jewelry to food, sweets, drinks, artistic performances, souvenirs, and services.

Necessity, according to a text from the online site Correioweb, is one of the reasons for the introduction of these entrepreneurs into the market. According

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to Sarah de Magalhães, the creator of Varanda BsB (a mobile flea market model), the advantages of the nomadic business are endless: "It's about exploring new places, experiencing new things, and there's also the fact that there are no fixed monthly costs, because the costs to maintain a collaborative store, for example, are very high. It's definitely much more expensive" (CorreioWeb).

Entrepreneurial metamodel from Filion's perspective

One of Filion's criticisms lies in the use of strategic models used in entrepreneur training that are mostly derived from those developed for large companies (Filion, 1993) and that these contain factors that are not important in the strategic process of small entrepreneurs.

This raises another question regarding applicability: what if we tried to take this sample to even smaller entrepreneurs at the micro or nano-entrepreneur level in the universe of entrepreneurship?

Filion provides contributions to the strategic thinking of the entrepreneur by presenting research conducted over five years (1985-1990) with 51 small entrepreneurs and eight owners of large companies in Finland, Sweden, Scotland, Switzerland, and Canada.

An initial criticism lies in the sampling, which takes place in the countries Finland, Sweden, Scotland, Switzerland, and Canada. That is, in countries with cultures and markets very different from the Brazilian market. Another criticism, to be considered, concerns the date and period in which the research was carried out, which occurred over a five-year period (between 1985 and 1990). In that time frame, much has changed, from products and technologies to consumer behavior and globalization. Regarding company size, in Brazil, companies are classified according to two criteria: revenue or number of employees. Micro-enterprises, for example, have an annual gross revenue of up to R\$ 360,000 or employ up to 9 people in commerce or 19 in the industrial sector. Those classified as small

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businesses have an annual income greater than R\$ 360,000 and less than or equal to R\$ 4.8 million per year, or employ between 10 and 49 people in commerce and services or between 20 and 99 people in industry. In Filion's work, companies classified as small are defined by the number of employees, which is between 50 and 250, with the exception of four, which are in the industrial sector, and which, from a universe of 51 small entrepreneurs and eight large Canadian companies. Therefore, if applied to the Brazilian market, the companies surveyed would be small and medium-sized enterprises (annual revenue greater than R\$ 4.8 million and less than or equal to R\$ 300 million) employing 50 to 99 people in the trade and services sector, and 100 to 499 people in the industry.

By mentioning that some members of the initial sample were eliminated for failing to maintain profitability or growth above a certain average, or for not proving sufficiently innovative, it seems to suggest that the author follows the premise that to be an entrepreneur, one must be innovative.

He uses the term "metamodel" from the perspective of Stafford Beer and John P. Van Gich. The Finnish cases were used in the development of the model, and the other countries to confirm its functionality.

The definition of the term 'metamodel' used in Filion's work comes from the perspective brought by Beer and Gich: "a model with a higher level of abstraction, which transforms the properties of lower-level systems into propositions of the higher-level abstraction model".

Filion's metamodel involves the development and realization of three categories of vision: emergent (a vision formed from ideas and concepts of products and/or services imagined by the entrepreneur), central (the result of a single vision or the combination of several emergent visions, a continuation of the emergent vision), and complementary (a series of visions that support the central vision in its development). It conceptualizes vision and its importance for defining the foundations of the identified systems.

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The three categories of vision (emergent, central, and complementary) are apparently universally applicable. We believe they share characteristics with aspects of Brazilian entrepreneurs as well. Other factors brought up in the work as contributors to the development of vision, such as leadership, energy, and perceptions, seem to be common characteristics of entrepreneurship even among different authors, with vision serving as a reference point for where one wishes to go.

Filion addresses four elements that underpin the vision, highlighting the 'system of relationships' as the most important, followed by 'Weltanschauung' (worldview), 'energy', and 'leadership', defining and characterizing each one individually.

He emphasizes that the implications of the work affect the three areas of entrepreneurial activity: entrepreneurial action, research, and education for entrepreneurial activities.

The emerging vision cited by Filion leads us to observe entrepreneurs in the Brazilian market, especially new entrepreneurs, who consider the most diverse paths to entrepreneurship, but who, during the journey, follow an apparently safer path present in the central vision, which brings with it complementary visions that will give continuity and support to the venture.

Entrepreneurs and entrepreneurial skills

Entrepreneurial competencies are a set of knowledge, skills, and attitudes that allow one to create and maintain a business. "Competence is the set of correlated knowledge, skills, and attitudes that, in action, add value to the individual and the organization, to what we call delivery," this is the definition of Competence given by Queiroz (2008).

Some entrepreneurial competencies are: identifying opportunities, developing innovative solutions, taking calculated risks. Persuasion to achieve

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objectives, leadership, initiative. Skills: communication, resilience, flexibility, commitment, self-esteem, self-confidence, market perception, perseverance, respect, and empathy.

Understanding the definition and characteristics of an entrepreneur is not an easy task and has therefore demanded work from many researchers and scholars on the subject, with diverse approaches and paths. There are countless definitions found.

Several authors have made contributions, such as: Boyatzis (1982), Le Boterf (2003), Woodruffe (1991), Parry (1986), Zarifian (1996), McLagan (1997). In Brazil, we have Dutra (2001, 2004), Fisher (2001), Fleury Afonso (2000), Fleury Maria (2000, 2001) and Leme (2008), cited by Queiroz (2008), among others.

Queiroz (2008) lists a set of sixteen competencies, with descriptions of the knowledge, skills, and attitudes that he considers to make up the profile of the professional of the future: Written Communication, Spoken Communication, Creativity/Innovation, Entrepreneurship, Information Management, Change Management, Leadership, Negotiation, Customer Orientation, Results Orientation, Intrapersonal Relationship, Interpersonal Relationship, Decision Making, Teamwork, Strategic Vision, and Systemic Vision.

In the BTE – Entrepreneur Thematic Library (<http://www.bte.com.br>), in a text prepared by Adriane Alvarenga da Rocha Pombo, from SEBRAE – Brazilian Service of Support to Micro and Small Enterprises, we find the definition of entrepreneur as: “Being an entrepreneur means, above all, being an achiever who produces new ideas through the congruence between creativity and imagination”. Added to the definition by Maria Inês Felipe:

This is someone capable of surprising company members, always ready to bring and manage new ideas, products, or change everything that already exists. They are an optimist who lives in the future, transforming crises into opportunities and influencing people to guide them towards their ideas. They are the ones who create something new or innovate what already exists and are always researching. They are

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the ones who seek new businesses and opportunities with a focus on improving products and services. Their actions are based on market needs (<http://www.bte.com.br>).

In chart 1, Dornelas (2007) presents a compilation, without proposing the extinction of the discussion on the subject, of reviews carried out by various researchers on some of the main entrepreneurial characteristics.

Chart 1 - Main Entrepreneurial Characteristics (by various authors)

Year	Author	Key entrepreneurial characteristics found
1848	Mill	Risk-taking
1917	Weber	Formal authority
1934	Schumpeter	Innovation, initiative
1954	Sutton	Desire for responsibility
1959	Hartman	Formal authority
1961	McClelland	Risk-taking, need for achievement, optimism, relationships (affiliation), power, self-awareness
1963	Dauids	Ambition, desire for independence, responsibility, self-confidence
1964	Pickle	Focus, relationships, communication skills, technical knowledge
1969	Gould	Perception of opportunity, motivated by achievement
1969	Wainer & Rubin	Achievement, power and affiliation
1970	Collins & Moore	Satisfaction and pleasure in what one does
1970	Hornaday & Bunker	Need for achievement, intelligence, creativity, initiative, leadership, desire to earn money, desire for recognition, achievement-oriented, power, tolerance for uncertainty
1971	Palmer	Risk assessment
1971	Hornaday & Aboud	Need for achievement, autonomy/independence, family history, aggressiveness, power, recognition, innovation, independence
1972	Draheim	Experience, credibility
1972	Howell	Influences (reference models)
1973	Winter	Need for power
1974	Borland	Self-control
1974	Liles	Need for achievement
1977	Gasse	Oriented to personal values
1978	Timmons	Focused/centered, self-confidence, goal-oriented, calculated risk, self-control, creativity, innovation
1979	DeCarlo & Lyons	Achievement, independence and leadership
1980	Brockhaus	Propensity to take risks
1980	Hull, Bosley & Udell	Interest in fame and money, self-control, propensity to take risks, creativity, achievement
1980	Sexton	Energy/ambition, positive reaction to failure (overcoming)
1981	Hisrich & O'Brien	Self-discipline, perseverance, desire for success, action-oriented, goal-oriented

(continues)

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Chart 1 - Main Entrepreneurial Characteristics (by various authors) - continuation

Year	Author	Key entrepreneurial characteristics found
1981	Mescon & Montanari	Achievement, autonomy, dominance, control, organization
1981	Welsch & White	Need to control, search for responsibility, self-confidence, takes on challenges, calculated risk
1982	Dunkelberg & Cooper	Growth-oriented, sense of independence, specialization
1982	Welsch e Young	Self-control, Machiavellianism, self-esteem, takes risks, open to innovation, optimism

Source: Dornelas (2007)

Dornelas (2007) presents us with eight types of entrepreneurs, each with their own characteristics. They are: born, learner, serial, corporate, social, necessity-driven, heir, and "normal."

Born entrepreneurs are generally the best known and most acclaimed. With brilliant stories, they start from scratch and create empires, beginning to work very early. Visionaries, optimists, ahead of their time. The learner entrepreneur is a type who has come across a business opportunity and makes the decision to dedicate themselves to their own business. The serial entrepreneur is passionate about the companies they create, but mainly about the act of entrepreneurship. A dynamic person who is not content to create a business and stay at its head until it becomes a large corporation (Dornelas, 2007).

The corporate entrepreneur works with an eye on results to grow in the corporate world. Skilled communicators and salespeople of their ideas, they are ambitious and know how to self-promote. Social entrepreneurs have the mission of building a better world by engaging in humanitarian causes and find fulfillment in seeing their projects bring results to other people. Of all types, they are the only ones not concerned with personal financial gain. The necessity entrepreneur undertakes ventures out of necessity, and the only remaining option is to become an entrepreneur. They are generally involved in informal businesses with simple tasks and service provision. Finally, we have the heir entrepreneur, who receives

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the mission of continuing the family business with the challenge of multiplying the inherited wealth (Dornelas, 2007).

Five-V tool by Taran et al.

Large companies are realizing that their current Business Models can easily become obsolete, such as Kodak and Blockbuster (Taran et al. 2016). It is necessary to design a more appropriate ontological scheme and a viable Business Model innovation.

In their article, Taran et al. (2016) provides a brief historical overview of the various studies that document the term Business Model since the mid-1990s (the 'dot-com' era), and many companies have begun to rethink their business structures, and the notion of Business Models is not entirely new.

The objective of Taran et al.'s research is twofold: to develop the meaning and content of each identified Business Model configuration, grouping these configurations into appropriate categories in a scientifically valid process; and through an ontological classification scheme to facilitate companies in the Business Model innovation process.

It highlights the most valid Business Model configuration approach as that of Gassmann et al. (1914) with a list of 55 Business Model patterns.

For Taran et al., classifying objects into homogeneous categories is a very relevant activity, and that categorizations are useful in the field of Business Model research, and that current categorizations are considered 'partially structured'. The literature was thoroughly reviewed by a multidisciplinary academic team, where works based on citations and well-known influential academics were selected, resulting in more than 120 articles carefully examined in the initial phase. This subsequently resulted in 97 Business Model configurations. Due to its popularity among developed businesses, entrepreneurs, and academics, the Business Model Canvas was chosen as a

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mapping tool, resulting in a final list of 71 Business Model configurations. The final categorization list resulted in: Value Proposition, Value Segment, Value Configuration, Value Network, and Value Capture.

Regarding the evolution of research in Business Models, it can be categorized into five main phases: phase one (various authors suggested definitions and classifications), phase two (concern with completing the definitions and proposing elements belonging to a Business Model), phase three (detailed description of the components), phase four (researchers modeled the components), and phase five (models were applied to management and information system environments).

Through the analysis and study of various business models and various recognized authors, in a consistent ontology, Taran et al. created the tool (Five-V) which, structurally more 'visual', contributes to the innovation of business models of various ventures.

The Five-V tool is a Business Model improvement and innovation tool by Taran et al. (2016). A Business Model tool based on value creation composed of five components: value proposition, value segment, value configuration, value network, and value capture. This demonstrates the need for operationalization within a viable ontological approach to the list of 71 Business Model configurations classified into five groups. The study's synthesis suggests that a Business Model should communicate five elements: What the company offers (Value Proposition); to whom the company is offering it (Value Segment); how the company develops and distributes this offer economically (Value Network); and how much and in what way the company generates revenue (Capture Value).

This tool brings together various business models, becoming an efficient tool that innovates in the business model, enabling a view of the current business model and, through innovation, an improvement in the business model to be

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used. Although it is used with medium to large enterprises, we believe in its potential for use in nano, micro, and small enterprises.

The Business Model innovation structure is divided into four stages: Stage 1, where the company's current state is observed and its processes are mapped; Stage 2, with a new BM design with a research and evaluation process, SWOT analysis with improvement indicators; Stage 3, selection of BM components, innovation and development of an action plan; and Stage 4, which is the implementation of the action plan.

The work of Taran et al. (2016) had the general objective of strengthening the understanding of researchers and professionals about Business Model configurations and proposing a method to use these configurations structurally, innovating in existing Business Models. Its main contribution was the grouping of these configurations into categories based on a structural, analytical and scientifically valid process. In the Business Model innovation process, working with 'Value Generators' allows managers to identify aspects that drive value creation in their Business Model, enabling them to maintain a competitive position in the market.

METHOD

This study adopted a case study approach to analyze the AbA Arte Design nano-enterprise, exhibited in a collaborative store in Brasília-DF. The period analyzed ranges from the creation of the brand in 2016 to January 2025, covering the trajectory of the enterprise and its transformations over time.

The Five-V tool, proposed by Taran et al. (2016), was used as a methodological basis for mapping and analyzing the five categories of value configurations: Value Proposition, Value Segment, Value Configuration, Value Network, and Value Capture. The application of the tool resulted in the

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elaboration of graphic representations of the current and proposed business models, allowing a clear visualization of the changes necessary for innovation.

The research was based on three main pillars: primary data, secondary data, and literature review. Primary data were collected directly from the AbA Arte Design nano-enterprise through interviews, observations, and analysis of internal documents. Secondary data were obtained from informational materials from the collaborative store where the venture is located, as well as from sources related to the context of collaborative stores and nano-entrepreneurship, contributing to the contextualization and understanding of the current business model.

The literature review complemented the study, bringing theories, models, and examples related to business models, entrepreneurial skills, and the Five-V tool. This step was essential to adapt the tool to the specific context of the nano-enterprise, ensuring the applicability of the analysis categories proposed by Taran et al. (2016).

The qualitative nature of the research allowed for an in-depth understanding of the entrepreneurial behavior necessary for remodeling the business with a focus on innovation. In addition, the work incorporated emerging concepts in the context of the Brazilian economy, highlighting the relationship between small business entrepreneurship and the use of innovative tools.

Finally, the study identified the essential entrepreneurial skills for implementing the new business model in the nano-enterprise analyzed, contributing both to entrepreneurial practice and to theoretical advancement in the area.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Five-V tool

The Five-V tool by Taran et al. (2016) is strongly structured around Value configurations for business modeling. There are five value principles: Value Network, Value Segment, Value Proposition, Value Configuration, and Value Capture.

In the Value Network, the network of partners for achieving economic scale, reducing risks, and leveraging new knowledge or resources is identified. This principle answers the question "Who?". In the Value Segment, which answers the question "For Whom?", the segment or portion of customers that the venture seeks to serve is highlighted. In the Value Configuration, the question "How?" can be answered with the combination of personnel, infrastructure, financial resources, production activities, sales, service, logistics, and distribution channels necessary to create and deliver the value proposition to the selected value segment. Value Capture answers the question "How much?" from the perspective of recovering how and how much customers are willing to pay for the products and services offered by the venture. And lastly, represented as the center of valuation, we have the Value Proposition, answering the question "What?", referring to the offer of products and services provided to customers and for which they are willing to pay.

Figure 1 seeks to provide a simpler and clearer graphical representation of the value points and the completion of the Five-V tool in a more comprehensive way. This same representation was used for the application of the tool with the AbA Arte Design nano-entrepreneurship case study in the construction of the current business model and the innovative business model to be applied.

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Figure1 – Five-V ontological Framework

Source: Taran et al. (2016)

Figure 2 – Graphical representation adapted from the Five-V Business Model tool for exploration in this work

Source: adapted from Taran et al. (2016)

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Analysis of the current model using the Five-V tool

AbA Arte Design is a for-profit micro-enterprise operating in the creative economy sector, located in the Federal District in a collaborative store called Endossa, offering products such as posters, mugs, notebooks, pens, pencils, magnets, decorative tiles and paintings, photographs, keychains, diaries, bags, buttons, calendars, t-shirts, postcards, stamps, gifts and souvenirs, among other customizable products.

Its clientele is diverse, ranging from enthusiasts, visitors, and tourists to architects, designers, and decorators.

Some of the brand's problems include its advertising and promotion, lack of a direct channel with the customer, costs associated with the collaborative store's administrative fees, mixing personal and business finances, inability to handle large orders, lack of presence in different locations, and limitations regarding logistics and delivery services.

Figure 3 – Current business model of the AbA Arte Design nano-enterprise

Source: adapted from Taran et al. (2016)

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Considering the current business model with the application of the Five-V tool, we have as a value proposition the reference in good, cheap products with differentiated aesthetic value related to products connected to Brasília, such as souvenirs and stationery.

Currently, it serves a diverse niche of customers ranging from those looking for Brasília souvenirs to customers seeking products for decoration and consumables such as decorators, architects, designers, tourists, and visitors.

Still incipient in the online environment, the brand is limited to the physical environment with a rented space in a collaborative store. Most products are produced by the entrepreneur himself, and others by print shops and product personalization companies.

A value network is identified with occasional partnerships with companies, print shops, and agencies for the production of giveaways and brand promotion.

The products have very low prices compared to similar ones in the market, and according to salespeople at the collaborative store, prices could be higher considering the perceived value by customers who would be willing to pay more for the products.

Currently, the brand is remembered because of the “printed” products with images associated with Brasília, marginalizing products with other images and other approaches, niches that can be explored. The rented physical space ends up limiting the size and quantities/stock of displayed products.

The biggest impacts related to challenges and problems, considering the proposition, segment, configuration, network, and value capture, are the scarcity of sales and product pickup points; potential customers rarely visit the location area of the business; lack of knowledge and difficulty accessing locations where the products are exhibited and sold; distancing from potential influencers and

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customers; high rental costs and administrative fees in different physical collaborative store spaces.

Opportunities were identified, considering the same values (proposition, segment, configuration, network, and capture), such as occupying differentiated spaces for product exhibition and sale, attracting tourists, visitors and enthusiasts, expanding spaces for exhibition and sales, approaching influencers, event promoters, exhibition promoters, and entrepreneurs, and registering/occupying virtual spaces for the sale of creative products.

The use of the Five-V tool experienced the generation of two ideas in its innovation space that can increase sales volume: briefly, promotion in online sales spaces and the expansion and diversification of physical spaces with greater flow of tourists, visitors, and enthusiasts.

Figure 4 – Innovation in the Business Model of the Microenterprise AbA Arte Design Using the Five-V Tool

Source: adapted from Taran et al. (2016)

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The new business model shows that the Value Proposition for the nanoenterprise AbA Arte Design is the presentation and sale of new products with themes already present and the creation of new themes/niches.

The search for potential customers such as architects, decorators, interior designers, artists, entrepreneurs, tourists, and enthusiasts (parts of the Value Segment) is essential in the development of the enterprise.

Since Value Capture presents disproportionate costs for a nanoenterprise, alternatives or cost reductions should be sought to increase profit.

New physical and virtual points, flexible suppliers, and participation in fairs and events structure the Value Configuration of the enterprise.

Partnerships with image and decoration professionals (architects, artists, designers, artists) would expand the client portfolio, add value to the products increasing demand and revenue. Promotion with cultural and event promoters would also contribute to brand exposure and consequently increase demand for the brand's products. Partnerships with companies can strengthen sales and economic stability in the market.

Entrepreneurial behaviors necessary for the innovation of AbA Arte Design's business model

The success of the implementation of the Five-V tool in the nanoenterprise is intrinsically linked to the entrepreneurial behaviors between the AbA brand and the collaborative store environment. Innovation, flexibility, adaptation to arising challenges, and communication are attributes that enhance the application of the tool, maximizing value delivery.

Entrepreneurial characteristics such as Strategic Vision (Filion's Worldview, 1993), adaptability, creativity, customer focus (Filion's Vision),

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resilience (Energy), and Negotiation and Decision Making (Leadership, Filion, 1993) stood out in the new business model using the Five-V tool.

Chart 2 summarizes the characteristic entrepreneurial findings necessary for innovation at AbA Arte Design.

Chart 2 – Relationship between identified entrepreneurial characteristics and their framework within Filion's metamodel (1993)

Framework in Filion's Metamodel (1993)	Entrepreneurial Characteristic	Description	Importance
Vision	Adaptability	Ability to adjust to changes that arise in the personalized products niche, economic crises, and diverse demands.	Allows the brand to adapt to unforeseen events, market challenges, and changes in consumer behavior, ensuring business continuity. Creativity is the core of the AbA brand as it works with artistic and design products
	Creativity	Aptitude for innovation in personalization processes, products, and in the creation of images and trend lines in fashion, design, and architecture.	This entrepreneurial characteristic is crucial for the venture, contributing to overcoming obstacles and market changes
	Customer Focus	Alignment of deliverables with customer expectations.	Customer focus guides and defines the segmentation of the microenterprise concerning the types of products and images desired and expected by clients

(continues)

Chart 2 – Relationship between identified entrepreneurial characteristics and their framework within Filion’s metamodel (1993) - Continuation

Leadership	Negotiation	Ability to secure advantageous partnerships and supplier offers	Negotiating the purchase of good and inexpensive products increases the brand’s profit and reduces prices for customers, bringing greater fluidity to the development of the business
	Decision-making	Decision-making ability	The decision-making process leads to expense reduction, increased supply, and customer satisfaction
Energy	Resilience	Maintenance of operational stability even under the occurrence of adversities	Events such as economic crises, pandemics, and other unexpected situations can paralyze a business. Resilience breaks these constraints by keeping the business and its structure firm
Relation	Communication	Communication ability among participants in the buying, selling, and display cycle	Communication is a very important criterion for promoting and advertising products and services, increasing demand
Cosmovision	Strategic Vision	Ability to anticipate future trends in product personalization technologies and the launch of new products and new images (design)	It allows the offering of new products and new prints with competitive differentials aligned with customer demand

Source: elaborated by authors (2025)

The characteristics identified and listed above are fundamental to sustaining innovation and competitiveness of the AbA microenterprise, as well as facilitating the implementation of the business model.

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CONCLUSION

The comparative analysis between the current business model and the proposed model revealed that the realization of an innovative model requires a specific set of entrepreneurial competencies. These competencies encompass essential knowledge, skills, and attitudes for creating and sustaining a business, such as: opportunity identification, development of innovative solutions, initiative, risk-taking ability, communication skills, commitment, market awareness, respect, empathy, perseverance, and flexibility.

By referencing the competencies listed by Queiroz (2008), the following stand out as fundamental for implementing innovation through the Five-V tool: written and spoken communication, creativity and innovation (the latter with special emphasis given the context of a creative economy venture), entrepreneurship, information management, change management, leadership, negotiation, customer orientation, result orientation, intrapersonal and interpersonal relationships, decision-making, teamwork, strategic vision, and systemic vision.

This study demonstrated the feasibility of applying the Five-V tool, originally developed for medium and large companies, in contexts of small ventures such as micro-entrepreneurs, individual micro-entrepreneurs (MEIs), micro and small businesses. The combination of competencies proposed by Filion (1993) in his metamodel and the use of the Five-V tool by Taran et al. (2016) allowed a clear outline of the values necessary for innovation in the studied microenterprise, as well as the critical competencies for the success of its implementation.

Although the work focused on a microenterprise as a case study, it is believed that the Five-V tool can be adapted and applied to other small ventures. This adaptation paves the way for reflections on the implementation of innovative

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business models, applicable to different contexts and scales of enterprises, contributing to theoretical and practical advances in the field of management and entrepreneurship.

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ENDEREÇOS VISITADOS

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